

Research Analysis in Eclectic Theory (Kaboudan and Sfandiar)

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Abstract : Present research investigates eclecticism in Iranian theatre on the basis of eclectic theory. Eclectic theatre is a new theory in postmodernism. The theory appeared during 60th - 70th century in some theatres such as "Conference of the Birds". Special theatrical forms have been developed in many geographical- cultural areas of the world and are indigenous to that area. These forms, as compared with original forms, are considered to be traditional while being comprehensive, the form is considered to be national. Kaboudan and Sfandiar theatre has been influenced by elements of traditional form of Iran.

Keywords : eclectic theatre, theatrical forms, tradition, play

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